

Biology Undergraduate Research Day

Friday, April 12, 2024

CELEBRATING UNDERGRADUATE STUDENT RESEARCH

Friday, April 12th, 2024
9:30AM – 2:30 PM
Nideyinàn Building
231 Porter Hall

Department of Biology

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Bruce C. McKay
Chair and Professor
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April 8, 2024

Dear Class of 2024

On behalf of everyone in the Department of Biology, I would like to congratulate you on reaching an important milestone in your academic journey. This week, we will celebrate your hard work when you present your honours projects to the Department. I look forward to talking to you in person and seeing the excitement that research day brings. I know I speak on behalf of my colleagues when I say that we are proud of you.

It is hard to believe that only a few years ago you entered our program in the first year of the Covid-19 pandemic. You persevered in this new reality, and we now celebrate that accomplishment as we return to our pre-pandemic tradition. Our capstone experience is the pinnacle of our undergraduate program. You have gained important experience, learned valuable new skills and acquired the confidence to excel as you move onto the next stage in your life.

I congratulate you and offer the very best of wishes to you, our new alumni, in all of your future endeavors.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Bruce McKay". The signature is fluid and cursive, with a long horizontal stroke at the end.

Bruce McKay
Chair and Professor
Department of Biology
Carleton University

Research Day Schedule

- ❖ Welcome and Opening Ceremony – **9:30 a.m.**
- ❖ Poster Presentations – **9:35 a.m. – 10:45 a.m.**

Session A

Student Name	Poster #	Student Name	Poster #
Al Sayed, Reem	A-1	Nair, Ashwathi	A-18
Al-Maenie, Alameen	A-2	O'Donnell, William	A-19
Brzezinski, Hunter	A-3	Owusu, Nana	A-20
Dale, Liam	A-4	Paschink, DrueAnne	A-21
Dilmaghani, Sarah	A-5	Ramessur, Nishka Beersing	A-22
Dyck, Kas	A-6	Reda Gad, Caroline	A-23
Edwards, Benjamin	A-7	Reoch Larwill, Dawson	A-24
Field, Marie	A-8	Saidani, Sara	A-25
Frewen, Kaylie	A-9	Santana, Luz Victoria	A-26
Jelly, Gabrielle	A-10	Shaka, Seana	A-27
Khan, Sameer	A-11	Stabile, Cassandra	A-28
Khan, Yumna	A-12	St-Denis, Johanna	A-29
Mannion, Jazmin	A-13	Stotz, Tristyn	A-30
Marchand, Anne-Marie	A-14	Tassi, Bianca	A-31
Mari, Omar	A-15	Thach, Nyahoal	A-32
Mccormick, Lauryn	A-16	Walker, A'Ishah	A-33
McGlone, Meghan	A-17	Zakarian, Hovagim	A-34

- ❖ Break – **10:45 a.m. – 11:00 a.m.**
Vote
Take your seat during the break for the Five-Minute Thesis Competition

- ❖ **Five-Minute Thesis (5MT) – 11:00 a.m. – 12:00 p.m.**

Audience will have a chance to ask questions at the end of each 5MT presentation.

Student name	Presentation #
Carter, Remy	5MT-1
Ghadie, Myaa	5MT-2
Huckvale, Mackenzie	5MT-3
Manivannan, Sujitha	5MT-4
Mason, Katherine	5MT-5

- ❖ Break – **12:00 p.m. – 12:15 p.m.**

❖ Poster Presentations – 12:15 p.m. – 1:30 p.m.

Session B

Student Name	Poster #	Student Name	Poster #
Abu khajil, Dania	<u>B-1</u>	Liebig, Jason	<u>B-18</u>
Akinbile, Abdul Roqeeb	<u>B-2</u>	Marshall, Kyle	<u>B-19</u>
Ali, Ayan	<u>B-3</u>	McLean, Bradley	<u>B-20</u>
Bossert, Sophia	<u>B-4</u>	Moran, James	<u>B-21</u>
Cornthwaite, Emily	<u>B-5</u>	Morden, Eric	<u>B-22</u>
Correa, Chris	<u>B-6</u>	Morrison, Grace	<u>B-23</u>
Dalla Ali, Yasmeen	<u>B-7</u>	Nwabueze, Jacqueline	<u>B-24</u>
Desbiens, Julia	<u>B-8</u>	Phillips, Ally	<u>B-25</u>
Donohue, Margaret	<u>B-9</u>	Rice, Kinly	<u>B-26</u>
Erdely, Katherine	<u>B-10</u>	Rix, Tamaryn	<u>B-27</u>
Gessese, Tadesse	<u>B-11</u>	Saunders, Nolan	<u>B-28</u>
Huynh, Tianna	<u>B-12</u>	Shareef, Rizwan	<u>B-29</u>
Jenkins, Danielle	<u>B-13</u>	Singh, James	<u>B-30</u>
Kamm-Ramirez, Nadine	<u>B-14</u>	Steenbakkers, Marin	<u>B-31</u>
Lagrove, Kennedy	<u>B-15</u>	Sultan, Nooran	<u>B-32</u>
Laribi, Tarek	<u>B-16</u>	Velasquez, Jahnessa	<u>B-33</u>
Lemieux, Amelie	<u>B-17</u>	Wood-Lyons, Isabel	<u>B-34</u>

❖ Deliberation and Break – 1:30 p.m. – 1:45 p.m.

❖ Award Ceremony – 1:45 p.m. – 2:00 p.m.

Additional information for all attendees

- If you require directions to the Nideyinàn Building, please refer to the campus map link (carleton.ca/campus/map/#NN)
- Kindly arrive 10-15 minutes early to check in with your Program Administrators, Haiyun Bo and Sarah Anne Szabototh, to collect your name tag and set up your poster.
- Refreshments, such as pastries, coffee, and tea, will be provided for both Attendees and Judges.

Abstracts

Session A Poster Presentation

Al Sayed, Reem – A-1

Title: Does vitamin D increase fertility in PCOS patients?

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) affects millions of women worldwide, posing a significant barrier to fertility. Irregular ovulation and hormonal imbalances are common symptoms of PCOS which can disrupt ovarian function and reduce fertility. The impact of Vitamin D deficiency on PCOS-associated infertility is often overlooked. This research explores the correlation between Vitamin D levels and fertility outcomes in PCOS patients through a meta-analysis of 11 studies. Results suggest that there is a statistically significant relationship between fertility and vitamin D. Vitamin D may regulate reproductive hormones, improve insulin sensitivity, and reduce inflammation, thereby enhancing ovulation and menstrual regularity. Vitamin D supplementation or increased sun exposure could offer a promising alternative therapy for PCOS-related infertility by addressing the underlying problems. Understanding the role of Vitamin D in PCOS fertility may revolutionize treatment approaches, bridging a critical knowledge gap and offering hope for improved reproductive outcomes in affected individuals.

Brzezinski, Hunter – A-3

Title: Investigating the Cross-Stage impacts of High Temperatures during Egg Development in *Grylodes sigillatus* and *Acheta domesticus*

Temperature significantly influences metabolism and growth in insects. Most insects are ectothermic poikilotherms whose body temperature closely matches environmental temperature. While previous studies have primarily examined the impacts of constant temperature or acute stressful temperatures on survival and growth in insects, the extent to which early life thermal history affects cross-stage development remains unclear. Addressing this gap in knowledge, we distributed the eggs of two cricket species commonly raised as food and feed, *Grylodes sigillatus* and *Acheta domesticus*, across a thermal gradient ranging from 30°C to 44°C to assess relative hatching success and hatch rate. After hatching, all crickets were incubated at a constant temperature of 32°C and weighed weekly to assess the impacts of high temperature exposure during the egg stage on later development. Understanding these interactions will allow farms to make informed decisions on temperature conditions used in commercial cricket rearing.

Al-Maenie, Alameen – A-2

Title: Diseases Impact on Gut Microbiome's: Insights from Alzheimer's

The gut microbiome, a complex community of microorganisms residing in the human digestive tract, plays a crucial role in health and disease. My meta-analysis examines how autoimmune and neurodegenerative diseases influence gut microbiome composition of beneficial bacteria. Through a systematic review of 7 studies to analyze bacterial abundance in fecal samples from Alzheimer's patients and healthy controls, significant differences were identified. Notably, Alzheimer's patients exhibited a reduced presence of beneficial bacteria. My findings underscore the potential of the gut microbiome to affect disease pathways, suggesting that microbiome-targeted therapies could represent a novel approach for managing Alzheimer's and similar conditions. By highlighting the gut-brain axis's involvement in disease progression, my analysis opens new avenues for research into microbiome-centric treatment strategies.

Dale, Liam – A-4

Title: Collapsing populations; the effects of climate change on snow crabs

With the research goal of determining the effect of a warming climate on the snow crab species, the question of whether Snow Crabs in warmer waters experience molts sooner than those in colder water emerges. Central to the prosperity of Eastern Canada's culture, the snow crab population has been seeing alarming collapses, and questions are raised about whether the climate is truly to blame for the collapse of the snow crab population.

To answer whether snow crabs in warmer waters experience molt sooner than those in colder water, the analysis of seven papers was included. These papers noted significant effects of cold water on the time taken to reach terminal moult, indicating that the climate does likely have a factor on the decreasing crab populations and, without intervention, will likely impact the local eastern economy and have profound implications on the ecosystem.

Dilmaghani, Sarah – A-5**Title: Combating Alzheimer's with Bee Venom: Exploring the Potential of Apamin**

Alzheimer's disease, affecting millions globally, lacks a cure. Exploring natural compounds offers a potential route for therapeutic development. Bee venom, containing a neurotoxin known as apamin, has been identified as a potential candidate. Apamin's action on potassium channels suggests it could enhance neuronal communication and elevate acetylcholine levels, critical for memory and learning. In this study, we conducted a meta-analysis where we carefully reviewed 781 studies and identified ten relevant ones. The results consistently showed an improvement in memory function linked to apamin treatment in mouse models, though with differences in how strong the effects were. These findings emphasize the complexity of apamin's effects and the necessity for further research to understand its effectiveness and safety for human use. Challenges remain in determining optimal dosing, delivery methods, and long-term safety. Nonetheless, apamin presents a compelling natural option for Alzheimer's therapy, deserving further investigation.

Edwards, Benjamin – A-7**Title: E-Waste Microbial Communities: Taking the Long Read**

In 2022 alone, 62 million tonnes of electronic waste (e-waste) were produced, posing pressing environmental and economic challenges. E-waste serves as a novel microbial niche, exposing microbes to potentially harmful and valuable metals. However, microbial influence on metal fate in such environments remains poorly understood. In this study, DNA extraction from varying types of e-waste collected in 2022 from a local recycling facility was optimized. This was followed by 16S rRNA sequencing and whole community long-read DNA sequencing (metagenomics) to characterize the community via reproducible computational workflows including QIIME2, nf-core, and FeGenie, gaining valuable insights into iron transport, storage, and the use of siderophores within these communities. E-waste sludge samples were dominated (>50%) by *Marinobacter segnicrescens* while the e-waste dust was found to be more diverse, this diversity was however affected by kit bias ($p = 0.008$).

Dyck, Kas – A-6**Title: Birch leaves as minefields: Do caterpillars select shelter location based on plant trichome distribution?**

Neonate caterpillars experience high mortality rates due to the many challenges presented by their environments. One major challenge is overcoming plant defenses, such as leaf trichomes. I test the hypothesis that neonates of the masked birch caterpillar (*Drepana arcuata*) select specific regions of birch leaves (*Betula papyrifera*) to build their silk shelters based on trichome distribution. First, to test whether neonates show site preferences, I placed individual neonate *D. arcuata* on *B. papyrifera* leaves and recorded shelter location after 24 hours. There was preference for the adaxial side (upper surface), and leaf edges. Second, I assessed the distribution of trichomes on *B. papyrifera* leaves using light and electron microscopy. The density of glandular trichomes was higher on the abaxial side (lower surface), with no differences shown between leaf locations. Overall, my results show that neonate caterpillars actively selected regions of the leaf with lower trichome densities for shelter building.

Field, Marie – A-8**Title: Ingestion and Trophic Transfer of Microplastics in Freshwater Fishes in the Rideau River and Canal**

Microplastics (plastic particles, <5 mm – 1 μ m) are a prevalent pollutant in urban landscapes and aquatic ecosystems. This study intends to fill the current research gap in our understanding of microplastic ingestion in freshwater fishes. Our study aims to answer (1) if urbanization increases the number of microplastics ingested by fish, (2) if trophic transfer of microplastics occurs in fish, and (3) if feeding guild influences the number of microplastics ingested by fish. Study sites were selected along the Rideau River and Rideau Canal. A total of 51 fish were sampled from three locations across Ottawa in urban and non-urban landscapes. Gastrointestinal tracts from fish were removed and digested in 10% potassium hydroxide (KOH). Water samples were taken from each fish sampling location and digested using a wet peroxide digestion. Our results show there is a strong relationship between the number of ingested microplastics and fish feeding guild.

Frewen, Kaylie – A-9**Title: Exploring the differences in cross-jurisdictional urban recreational fisheries: A case study of the Detroit River**

The Detroit River crosses the Canadian-American border, with anglers from Windsor, ON and Detroit, MI fishing on either side. As a single waterbody that is cooperatively managed by two jurisdictions that enforce different fishery regulations, the Detroit River makes a compelling case study for exploring the impacts of differences in cross-jurisdictional management strategies on the catch and consumption behaviour of shoreline anglers. We surveyed 98 shoreline anglers in Windsor (n = 44) and Detroit (n = 54) concerning their awareness and adherence to consumption guides and found that Detroit anglers are more aware of, but less likely to follow fish consumption advisories. Interestingly, fish consumption advisories are made more accessible by the State of Michigan government. We conclude that differences in cross-jurisdictional management strategies impact the likelihood of anglers to follow safe consumption practices and may influence catch and consumption behaviour. Thus, we recommend more equitable policymaking for fishing

Khan, Sameer – A-11**Title: Investigating the Interactome of *Arabidopsis thaliana* MPKs: An Integrative Approach Using Multiple Sources of Evidence and Machine Learning-Based Structural Modeling**

The *Arabidopsis thaliana* mitogen-activated protein kinase (MPK) signaling network plays a role in various cellular processes. This study integrated protein-protein interaction, genetic interaction, and co-expression data from the STRING, BioGRID, and ATTED-II databases to provide a comprehensive dataset of interactions within the network. The key MPK network components from this set were identified and subjected to functional enrichment analysis, which revealed their involvement in diverse biological processes and pathways. The 3D structure of MKK2 was predicted using AlphaFold2, and protein-protein docking simulations were performed between MPK6 and MKK2. The docking analysis identified important residues mediating their interaction. This integrative approach, combining multiple sources of evidence, structural predictions, and protein-protein docking, provides a comprehensive approach for understanding the *A. thaliana* MPK signaling network. The findings demonstrate the complex regulatory mechanisms that play a role in plant stress responses and development.

Jelly, Gabrielle – A-10**Title: Fighting the Invasion: Can Established Invasive Fish be Removed from an Ecosystem?**

Invasive species can be detrimental to native environments and ecosystems. Spreading of disease, disrupting predator-prey interactions, and reducing native biodiversity are few of the many effects invasive species have on delicate environments. To combat the effects of invasive fish, I posed the question, is removing established invasive fish species from an ecosystem possible? I used a meta-analysis approach and screened through 609 articles. All articles had different research sites, different species, and different interventions. Using population data from the articles collected, I arranged the results onto a forest plot using a correlation analysis. The random effects model on the forest plot determined that removal of invasive species was possible. All articles showed a decline in invasive fish populations after intervention. Additionally, the various intervention methods used were widely applicable to invasive species removal. My results showed that removing fish is an effective method of invasive fish species control.

Khan, Yumna – A-12**Title: Multigenotypic Recombinant Antibodies Against Human Norovirus**

Human norovirus represents a significant global health concern, being the predominant cause of acute gastroenteritis worldwide, with approximately 685 million cases and 212,000 fatalities annually. The virus's genotypic diversity challenges the development of effective diagnostic strategies, vaccines and therapeutics. Our research leveraged advanced bioinformatics to identify three conserved epitopes across three prevalent norovirus genotypes, G I, G II, and GIV. These epitopes exhibit high immunogenicity and are pivotal for viral structural integrity and host-cell interaction. For experimental validation, the epitopes underwent solid-phase peptide synthesis resulting in the synthesis of two peptides. These peptides were used to screen a llama-based phagemid library. Further investigations successfully confirmed the antigenicity of the identified epitopes so that phages exhibiting high affinity for our target peptides could be isolated. This achievement holds promise for diagnostic applications and the development of targeted therapeutic interventions aimed at reducing the impact of norovirus infections.

Mannion, Jazmin – A-13

Title: Does Gypsum Impact Cereal Crop Yield in Sodic Soils?

To meet the growing demand on the world's food supply, farmers are looking for ways to improve poor quality soil, such as sodic soils. Gypsum, a common mineral, may provide the solution that these farmers are searching for. When gypsum is added to sodic soil, the sulfate in the gypsum binds with the sodium ions in the soil, producing the soluble salt sodium sulfate. The sodium can then be leached from the soil, improving the soil's overall quality and structure. The objective of this meta-analysis was to determine if gypsum treatment could improve the yields of cereal crops grown in sodic or saline-sodic conditions. Ten papers were included in this meta-analysis. Effect size was measured using Hedge's *g* and both the fixed-effect and random effect sizes were positive. The positive effect sizes support the theory that gypsum treatment increases cereal crop yields in sodic conditions.

Mari, Omar – A-15

Title: Optimizing Health and Performance: The Complementary Effects of Diet, Supplementation and Exercise

This comprehensive review examines the relationship between dietary needs, supplementation strategies and exercise regimens to analyze what prompts and optimizes health and performance. This paper focuses on the purpose of micronutrients such as vitamins and minerals and macronutrients such as proteins, fats and carbohydrates and the potential side effects of a lack or excess amount that is either produced or consumed as well as dietary supplements such as protein powder, pre-workout, branch chain amino acids (BCAAs), creatine and glutamine. Varieties of training regiments were overviewed such as endurance, hypertrophy and strength training to assess which resulted in an optimization of the individual's health. Hormone supplementation is also discussed with its pros and cons to highlight when they should be used and lastly the cumulative benefit of monitoring all these factors together to optimize the health and performance of the human body to improve metabolic processes, muscle building and weight management.

Marchand, Anne-Marie – A-14

Title: Wildlife Crossing Structures and Fencing: Worth the Effort?

Anthropogenic changes, notably vehicle-animal collisions, pose significant risks to wildlife and humans. Wildlife crossing structures such as overpasses, underpasses, and roadside fencing have been implemented globally to address this issue. These structures aim to facilitate safe wildlife passage across roads, but their effectiveness can vary depending on design, placement, and species preferences. This study evaluates the efficacy of wildlife crossing structures and fencing in mitigating wildlife-vehicle collisions. A systematic review of 542 research articles yielded 10 primary studies encompassing diverse wildlife species. Meta-analysis results indicate a significant decrease in wildlife-vehicle collisions overall, with the most effective measures observed for frogs and rattlesnakes. While the effectiveness varied among species, the findings underscore the importance of considering species preferences in designing and placing crossing structures. This research contributes to evidence-based decision-making for future mitigation strategies, aiming to reduce roadkill and minimize the negative impacts of human activities on wildlife populations.

Mccormick, Lauryn – A-16**Title: Boosting Physical Strength with Creatine Monohydrate: Insights from a Comprehensive Meta-Analysis**

The role of creatine monohydrate in enhancing physical strength has become a subject of extensive scientific exploration and practical interest within the athletic community. As a naturally occurring compound crucial for energy production in muscle cells, its supplementation has been hypothesized to significantly augment physical strength. This study, through an exhaustive meta-analysis, synthesizes findings from numerous studies to assess the veracity of claims surrounding creatine monohydrate's effectiveness in bolstering strength. By employing a structured PICO framework, the research scrutinizes the impact of creatine monohydrate supplementation versus no supplementation or placebo among individuals engaged in resistance training. The search, executed via the Web of Science, meticulously sieved through 1179 records, ultimately focusing on 14 studies deemed suitable for meta-analysis. The outcome of this analysis reveals a consistent positive effect of creatine supplementation on strength, evidenced by effect sizes greater than zero across most studies, alongside significant findings from both fixed and random effects models. These results compellingly suggest that creatine monohydrate, in conjunction with resistance training, indeed enhances strength. This revelation not only reinforces the supplement's value in sports nutrition but also underscores its potential in broader health and wellness strategies, particularly in contexts where physical strength is imperative. The synthesis of this data provides a robust foundation for recommending creatine monohydrate as an efficacious adjunct to resistance training regimens, promising significant implications for athletes, fitness enthusiasts, and individuals pursuing physical rehabilitation.

McGlone, Meghan – A-17**Title: Wheat Seedling Differences: Is this why Roblin gets sick?**

Pathogen resistance in plants has been a continuous topic of interest, especially agriculturally, however, only recently has that focus been dedicated to understanding the intricacies of how plant defense systems develop disease specific resistance. Little is known at a systematic level how different defense mechanisms are prioritized within a species or how this prioritization leads to the observed resistance. This unique research explores some of the morphological, protein and enzyme activity differences between 2 wheat cultivars (Fontana, resistant to Fusarium head blight and Roblin, susceptible) after exposure to stress when young to glean insight into the prioritizations necessary for disease-specific pathogen resistance. Our study found interesting differences in growth patterns, protein levels, lignin development, and glutamine synthetase activity between cultivars and stress exposure. Our findings highlight the complexity of plant defenses and the trade-offs to prioritization of pathogen resistance in wheat.

Nair, Ashwathi – A-18**Title: FURRY FRIENDS AS STRESS BUSTER: FACT OR FICTION?**

Pets and humans have maintained a relationship for centuries. This meta-analysis aimed to investigate pet ownership's influence on mental health and stress levels. It focuses on assessing the efficacy of pets in comparison with other therapeutics. The web search found 718 articles, of which 11 were taken since they were directly related to the research question (PICO statement). These 11 studies contributed data for the forest plot analysis; Random Effect: Pooled Effect size = 3.39, 95%ci= [-6.9,9.2], k=11 Tau² = 330.1. The analysis indicated that pet ownership had a positive effect on mental health, with most of the selected studies supporting the hypothesized role of pets in reducing stress levels. The study concluded that pet ownership can be beneficial, serving as companions and enhancing psychological resilience and social interactions.

O'Donnell, William – A-19**Title: Functional characterization of soybean early maturity E8 gene candidate in *Arabidopsis thaliana***

Soybean (*Glycine max*) is an important crop in Canadian agriculture especially in southern and eastern Canada. As demand for soybeans increases, there is a desire to expand growth northwards and westwards which is hindered by shorter growing seasons necessitating early maturity lines. Currently 11 maturity loci, classified as E series (E1-11) have been identified that influence soybean maturity, with most responding to red/far-red light. Most of the E series have been classified but E8 remains unknown. Glyma.04G124600, a predicted ortholog of the red-light perception gene FAR1 RELATED SEQUENCE 5 (FRS5) in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, is the best candidate gene for E8. Experiments exposing E8 and e8 soybean to red light suggest that e8 is insensitive to red light verifying that E8 is involved in red light perception. The goal of this project is to further test the E8 and e8 genes in red light perception using *Arabidopsis* as model plants.

Paschink, DrueAnne – A-21**Title: Chirping Tree-Killers: Sound Production in the Eastern Larch Beetle, *Dendroctonus simplex* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae)**

Bark beetles are of significant ecological and economical importance worldwide. Acoustic communication is proposed to predominate in their sensory ecology, although poorly understood. The Eastern Larch beetle, *Dendroctonus simplex*, causes major damage to Eastern Larch, *Larix laricina*, in Canada and the USA. This thesis is the first to explore sound production in this species. Wild-caught beetles were subject to pinch trials while recording with a microphone, and then subsequently studied for their sound producing mechanisms. Results showed that only males produce sound in this context. The stridulatory mechanism is elytra-tergal, with a file (*pars stridens*) on the left elytron rubbing against the 7th abdominal tergite (*plectrum*). Chirps- a series of sound pulses that result from the *plectrum* running along the *pars stridens*- were characterized as “simple” and “interrupted”. My results contribute to our understanding of the sensory ecology of this important species and may have applications in acoustic pest management.

Owusu, Nana – A-20**Title: Examining the Link Between Circadian Disruptions and Seasonal Affective Disorder Risk: A Meta-Analysis**

Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD) is a type of mood disorder that occurs during the fall and winter months when daylight hours are shorter. Individuals with SAD may experience symptoms such as low energy, oversleeping, weight gain, and a general feeling of hopelessness. The risk of developing SAD is influenced by disruptions in the circadian rhythm. Therefore, the relationship between disruptions in the circadian rhythm and the risk of developing SAD is profound, as it directly impacts an individual's mental well-being. We conducted a search using Web of Science to identify related studies examining the relationship between circadian disruptions and SAD. 11 studies met the inclusion criteria. Findings indicated a significant relationship between circadian rhythm disruptions and the risk of developing SAD. Individuals susceptible to developing SAD exhibited changes in circadian rhythms regulation. Understanding how seasonal changes affect circadian rhythm in individuals prone to SAD is essential for developing therapeutic strategies.

Ramessur, Nishka Beersing – A-22**Title: Investigating the Genotoxic Effects of Benzoic Acid in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae***

Benzoic acid, commonly present in microplastics, represents a significant environmental contaminant with potential adverse effects on biological systems and its impact on eukaryotic organisms, has been largely unexplored. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the influence of benzoic acid on gene functions within the model organism *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Upon exposure to a concentration of 12.5 mmol of benzoic acid, several key gene deletion mutants—NISB1, NISB2, NISB3, NISB4, and NISB5—were found to exhibit increased sensitivity. These genes are involved in crucial pathways, including DNA damage repair, DNA replication fidelity, and metabolic processes essential for the synthesis of vital amino acids. Previous literature suggests benzoic acid leads to genetic instability and compromised DNA repair. Furthermore, the involvement of NISB4, a gene of undetermined function, suggests that additional pathways might be affected by benzoic acid. This study thus raises questions about the health implications of microplastic-associated contaminants.

Reda Gad, Caroline – A-23**Title: Stress-Protein Expression during Heat-Shock and Hypoxia in the Yellow Perch (*Perca flavescens*)**

In a variable marine environment that is constantly affected by climate change, and anthropogenic activities, fish are constantly under stress. Changing water conditions will result in environments with higher temperatures and lowered oxygen which fish must respond to. In this paper, the expression of stress proteins during hypoxia and heat-shock in the yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*), will be studied by running 1-D gels containing liver samples from fish exposed to hypoxia, and heat shock conditions. Densitometry analysis was also conducted on the gel bands of interest to quantify their changes in expression. One-way ANOVA was run for quantitative analysis of band densities. Proteins extracted from gels were then run through mass spectrometry analysis for identification. Differentially expressed proteins between control and stress conditions, either upregulated or down regulated during stress, will be presented. This study aims to address the literature gap about proteomic expression of stress proteins in fish.

Saidani, Sara – A-25**Title: Unveiling the Spectrum of Post-Operative Complications in Pediatric Posterior Fossa Tumor Resections: Insights from Medulloblastoma and Astrocytoma Cases Across Time**

Our study delves into the complexities of post-operative complications following posterior fossa tumour resection procedures in paediatric patients, with a particular emphasis on cases of medulloblastoma and astrocytoma at three distinct intervals of time: immediate, 3-6 months, and 12 months post-surgery. Through an integration of clinical data analysis and advanced imaging techniques, our approach was to identify potential correlations between tumour type and the occurrence of complications, in addition to depicting the possible short- and long-term consequences on patients' health. Our findings suggest a strong correlation between tumour type and complications, with compelling parallels in the distribution of percentage gliosis across medulloblastoma and astrocytoma patients, albeit with notable outliers indicating heterogeneity within the astrocytoma sample. This study not only contributes to a deeper comprehension of the multifaceted challenges that paediatric patients encounter following surgery, but it also emphasises the crucial nature of individualised, patient-centered care techniques to optimise outcomes in this vulnerable group.

Reoch Larwill, Dawson – A-24**Title: Abnormalities in Ground Reaction Force and Gait in ACL-reconstructed Individuals**

Anterior Cruciate Ligament (ACL) tears are a common orthopaedic injury with a rising rate of reconstructive surgery in both males and females across age groups. Despite research regarding ACL reconstruction, little is known of the effects on Ground Reaction Force (GRF) and gait following surgery. The objective of this study was to evaluate any potential differences in GRF and gait between subjects' legs which underwent ACL reconstruction and legs which had no ligamental tear history. GRF was measured using a Bertec Force Plate for the purpose of finding the anteroposterior, mediolateral and vertical forces. Participants' gaits were recorded and measured via calculative functions within Tracker. Statistically significant abnormalities in heel-strike and toe-off, as well as GRF deficits were found between ACL-reconstructed legs and non-reconstructed legs. These results are important for understanding the long term effects of reconstructive surgery on leg function, and the potential need for more comprehensive rehabilitation strategies.

Santana, Luz Victoria – A-26**Title: Happy Gut, Happy Mind**

This research delves into the intriguing relationship between gut microbiota and mental health in adults. Utilizing a meta-analysis approach, the study used empirical evidence from 10 peer-reviewed articles, exploring the potential impact of gut microbiota on anxiety and depression. Through meticulous filtration, studies were selected based on strict criteria, including the use of PHQ-9 and GAD-7 standardized mental health assessments and human adult participants. The analysis revealed an ambiguous yet suggestive association between gut microbiota and mental health outcomes. Despite varying results, the collective evidence underscores the importance of further exploration in this flourishing field. This research sheds light on the complex interplay between gut microbiota and psychological well-being, offering insights into potential avenues for promoting mental health through dietary interventions and gut health management.

Shaka, Seana – A-27**Title: Virtual 3D Modeling of Calcification for Identifying FFT Risk in Carotid Stenosis**

Free-floating thrombi (FFT), occurs when plaque, in patients with significant stenosis, becomes detached from the arterial walls and moves freely within the bloodstream. Within 30 days of diagnosis, 17.1% of patients are at risk of a stroke, brain damage, or even death. Interestingly, carotid stenosis often shows an increase in blood velocity at the branching point (i.e., bifurcation). In theory, this increase in turbulence may damage the artery lining, potentially dislodging plaque, forming FFT. This study aims to determine whether a high calcification volume at the bifurcation of the ICA can serve as an indicator for FFT. Using virtual reality (VR), we segmented 60 ICA models (30 with FFT) from patients with $\geq 50\%$ stenosis. Our analysis revealed a correlation between increased calcification volume at the bifurcation and FFT occurrence. Our findings suggest VR-based 3D segmentation of calcification volume has the promising future in FFT diagnosis and prevention.

St-Denis, Johanna – A-29**Title: Hydrangeas in the Fight Against Diabetes**

Diabetes has become a global crisis; the treatment of the chronic disease had become a primary concern. In Canada alone, an estimated thirty percent of the population lives with some form of diabetes. Diabetes has a range of complications, including heart attacks, strokes, kidney failure and non-traumatic amputations. Medication, such as insulin injections, is the predominant regimen. However, ongoing medication shortages hinder treatment. Thus, an alternative medication treatment made from hydrangeas may be the solution. Here, I conduct a meta-analysis of the current knowledge about the use of chemical compounds derived from the *Hydrangea* genus and their effect on the glycemic index of mice. I also discuss the decrease in the glycemic index in each study following the treatments of the chemical compounds from *Hydrangea macrophylla*, *H. serrata*, and *H. paniculata*. Finally, I suggest the potential ramifications of alternative medical treatments that may also apply regarding human-use. Health through dietary interventions and gut health management.

Stabile, Cassandra – A-28**Title: The impact of chilling injury on sterile immune activation in a model insect**

Chill-susceptible insects are increasingly exposed to instances of cold climate through poleward range expansion. Low-temperature exposure to such insects causes chilling injuries, which are associated with decreased fitness (e.g., locomotion defects). Additionally, low-temperature stress is linked to an upregulation of immune responses. The release of intracellular contents from damaged cells causes a cascade of signalling in immune pathways known as sterile immune activation. With sterile immune activation emerging as an area of research in many organisms, it is essential to understand the mechanism linking this response to chilling injury. We developed chill coma recovery and survival data for *G. sigillatus* and tested whether cold stresses that cause tissue damage in crickets also induce upregulation of selected immune genes across Toll, Imd, and Jak/STAT signalling pathways. We hypothesized that injury presentation

Stotz, Tristyn – A-30**Title: Multi-Drug Resistance: Is Targeted Therapy More Effective Than Chemotherapy?**

Targeted therapy marks a pivotal advancement in cancer treatment, showcasing enhanced precision and effectiveness against multi-drug resistance (MDR), a significant challenge for conventional chemotherapy. Unlike chemotherapy, which affects cancerous and healthy cells, targeted therapy focuses on specific molecular targets involved in cancer progression. Targeted therapy minimizes side effects by sparing normal cells and can form a response to combat MDR. In a meta-analysis, we collected measurements of MDR tumours from research to determine if targeted therapy is more effective than chemotherapy. Our findings show that targeted therapy is more effective in overcoming MDR, offering a promising avenue for more effective cancer treatment. This presentation discusses the complexity of MDR, alongside the principles of targeted therapy and chemotherapy, to determine the preferred approach in combating MDR, potentially revolutionizing cancer management strategies.

Tassi, Bianca – A-31**Title: Using Genomics to Estimate Jack Pine Resiliency to Mountain Pine Beetle in the Boreal Forest**

Jack pine is a cornerstone tree species in the boreal forest and a newly discovered host for the mountain pine beetle (MPB). As the climate changes and the extent of human activity in the forest increases, patterns of MPB outbreaks are shifting. This leads to questions on whether the range of MPB could further extend into jack pine habitats in Canada. In this study, a multi-locus, per individual, polygenic risk score (PRS) was calculated for jack pine, lodgepole pine, and hybrid trees using 198 SNP loci previously identified as being associated with resilience to MPB in lodgepole pine. This was followed by spatial mapping of these risk scores on the Canadian landscape, and statistical analysis comparing lodgepole and jack pine scores. PRS analysis may help identify at-risk jack pine stands and facilitate the establishment of suitable conservation measures to control the potential spread of MPB across the boreal forest.

Walker, A'Ishah – A-33**Title: Could HLA-C be Used to Predict Odds of Psoriasis and Related Disease.**

Psoriasis is an autoimmune condition that affects 2-3% of the world population or around 125 million people. Psoriasis is associated with arthritis, uveitis, heart disease and other illnesses. Within a few years psoriasis can cause permanent damage, loss of quality of life, and disability. Psoriasis can be difficult to diagnose, as symptoms are hard to connect to the disease and there is no one test for psoriasis. HLA-C is part of the genome involved in mediating immune function. HLA-C is associated with psoriasis in genetic testing and has been suggested as a candidate for diagnostic tests. For this meta-analysis I analyzed data from 25 articles across the globe discussing psoriasis and HLA-C to determine if HLA-C increases the odds of psoriasis. Based on a log odds ratio and forest plot I was able to determine that there is no significant connection between psoriasis and HLA-C.

Thach, Nyahoal – A-32**Title: Detection of Salmonella using Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering**

Surface-enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) has become a valuable technique for quick and sensitive Salmonella detection. This innovative biosensing method offers precise identification of pathogens, essential for ensuring food safety and clinical diagnoses, while also increasing the speed of detection compared traditional methods like plate counting. Using nanoparticles to enhance signal intensity, aptamer-based assays are able to achieve accurate target recognition. Gold nanoparticles and quantum dots enable signal amplification required for pathogen detection through conventional methods, while also allowing for more convenient on-site SERS-based approaches through mobile applications. The success of the assay relies on the compatibility of the aptamers and nanoparticles with the sample, so careful consideration should be shown to what kind of materials are used. Overall, SERS techniques demonstrate promising capabilities in sensitivity, specificity, and selectivity for biosensing technology.

Zakarian, Hovagim – A-34**Title: Broken Alarm Clocks: Temporal Mismatches between Springtime Bee and Flower Emergence**

Bees and plants exist in a symbiotic relationship in which bees feed on plants and plants are pollinated by bees. Spring emergence times lining up between the two species is imperative for the mutual benefit and survival of both parties. However, climate change may cause desynchronization between the emergence times for the two different groups since the environmental cues which each group uses may no longer be correlated with the other group's cues. This meta-analysis finds that the emergence times of bees and their plant partners are experiencing significant desynchronization in their emergence times as the climate deviates from historical trends.

5-Minute Thesis Competition (5MT)

Carter, Remy – 5MT-1

Title: miRNA Biogenesis in Estivated *Otala lactea*

Otala lactea is an estivating land snail. Estivating animals are characterized by the global depression of most of their metabolic activities during dormancy. Considering the induction into estivation takes place quickly, miRNAs are likely integrally involved due to their regulatory effects being accurate, potent, and long-lasting. Western blotting was used to investigate the differential expression of 18 proteins involved in miRNA biogenesis of the snail in the control vs. 10-day estivated states for the hepatopancreas and the foot muscle tissues. DGCR8 was downregulated and XPO5 was upregulated in the hepatopancreas tissue, where it was suggested that miRNA biogenesis is initially upregulated but will gradually depress over time past the 10th day of estivation due to nuclear pre-miRNA depletion. DROSHA and RanGTP were upregulated and TRBP was downregulated in the foot muscle, where it was suggested that miRNA biogenesis rapidly diminishes past the 10th day of estivation via ubiquitination of DROSHA.

Huckvale, Mackenzie – 5MT-3

Title: Analysis of hydrolase enzyme's ability to degrade commercially available PLA-based biodegradable plastics

Biodegradable plastics are often presented as a solution to the increasing burden of plastics on human and environmental health. However, challenges remain in optimizing their biodegradability at an industrial scale. Here, we use a spectrophotometric-based assay to screen commercially available protease and lipase enzymes for the ability to degrade a commercial biodegradable plastic. We find that protease and lipase enzymes of unknown mechanisms can significantly degrade the plastic compared to no-enzyme controls. We show that mixing hydrolase enzymes of same and different sub-classes at varying ratios can also promote biodegradable plastic degradation. Further investigation shows Ca²⁺ ions can act as an additive cofactor to improve protease-mediated degradation. A cost-benefit analysis of screened treatments shows relative degradation can reach 64-88% of that achieved by "gold-standard" Proteinase K for 7-15% of the cost. These results highlight the potential of optimized, cost-effective enzymes as a commercially feasible strategy for industrial-scale biodegradable plastics degradation.

Ghadie, Myaa – 5MT-2

Title: A Quantitative PCR Method for Evaluating Plasmid Loss in Passaged Enterobacteriaceae Strains

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global health crisis. Many AMR genes (ARGs) are transferred between organisms via horizontal gene transfer methods, like conjugation. Although, in theory, most plasmids confer a metabolic disadvantage to the host and should be incorporated into the chromosome, most plasmids persist within their host, a phenomenon called the 'plasmid paradox.' As ARGs are often transferred within and between bacterial populations via plasmids, understanding the dynamics of plasmid transfer, persistence, and evolution within bacteria is critical. Most methods for monitoring plasmid persistence are time-consuming and low-throughput, based on bacterial cell cultivation and colony differentiation followed by confirmed detection of the target plasmid. Here, we have optimized a real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR) method for monitoring plasmid persistence in pure cultures of Gammaproteobacteria. We measured the persistence of an AMR plasmid encoding the 3rd generation cephalosporin resistance gene bla_{CMY-2} utilizing the qPCR method and compared it to plate counts.

Manivannan, Sujitha – SMT-4**Title: Investigating Synergistic Antifungal Potential of Propionic Acid**

Considering the critical issue of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), this study investigates activity of a promising antifungal agent, propionic acid (PPA). PPA has been reported to disrupt cell membrane functions which, we reasoned, may increase susceptibility to other antifungals. The combinatorial effects of PPA were investigated together with four antifungal drugs across eight fungal species using checkerboard assays. Varying degrees of synergy and antagonism were observed among antifungal-propionic acid combinations. Especially high synergy was observed with Ketoconazole-PPA and Amphotericin B-PPA combinations in *Verticillium dahliae*. The effect of sub-inhibitory concentrations of PPA on fungal endocytosis was analyzed by uptake of Lucifer Yellow (LY) dye. No significant increase in LY uptake was observed with this study. Further research should investigate PPA's antifungal mechanism of action and potential off-target effects on hosts of pathogenic fungi. Understanding PPA's action could encourage its application as a synergistic antifungal with conventional medications, aiding in combating AMR.

Mason, Katherine – SMT-5**Title: Evaluating the benefits of avian biodiversity on human mental health**

Exposure to nature provides mental health benefits, yet the role of biodiversity is unresolved. Well-being may be more closely tied to people's perception of species diversity, which may not align with objective measurements. In 2023, 212 adults in Detroit, USA completed surveys that measured mental health metrics, perception of neighbourhood bird diversity, nature relatedness, and socio-demographic information. Acoustic recordings were collected from 110 random sites, which were used to determine objective bird species diversity. Study participants were 87.0% Black and 44.3% unemployed. I found a positive relationship between perceived and objective bird species richness ($p = 0.051$) and between nature relatedness and perceived stress ($p = 0.001$). There was no relationship between metrics of diversity and mental health. Results indicate that participants accurately identify biodiversity in their neighbourhoods, which may indicate low overall biodiversity. Additionally, individuals may feel increased stress because they are unable to connect with neighborhood nature.

Session B Poster Presentation

Abu khajil, Dania – B-1

Title: Chronic Cannabis Use Effect On Long-Term Memory: A Meta-Analysis

In recent years, the conversation surrounding cannabis has been focused on its benefits, overshadowing potential risks associated with its chronic use. This meta-analysis examines the effect of chronic cannabis use on long term memory. I gathered data from various studies to gain a deeper understanding on this topic. My analysis shows that people who chronically use cannabis have a worse long-term memory which is evident by poorer performance on memory tasks among chronic users compared to non-users. This is due to cannabis disrupting normal neural functioning, particularly within the hippocampus, our memory centre. Chronic use of cannabis can even change the structure of the hippocampus, making it difficult to store long-term memories. The key takeaway is to use cannabis in moderation to protect your memory. It's essential to make smart choices about cannabis use to protect your cognitive functions.

Ali, Ayan – B-3

Title: The Mediterranean Diet's Influence on Gut Health

In my study, I explored how our choice of diet influences the health of our gut. I compared the Mediterranean diet, full of fruits, vegetables, and grains, with the Western diet, often high in processed foods. The results were striking the Mediterranean diet increased the variety and boosted the number of beneficial gut bacteria and enhanced the production of anti-inflammatory substances. Conversely, a Western diet led to less diversity among gut bacteria and higher inflammation levels. Therefore, I conclude that embracing the Mediterranean diet could be key to a healthier gut and disease prevention. My research suggests making choices aligned with the Mediterranean diet is essential for gut health.

Akinbile, Abdul Roqeeb – B-2

Title: Identification of Differentially Expressed Genes in Cold-Acclimated Fruit Flies

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are noncoding small RNA molecules that regulate post-transcriptional gene expression through sequence-directed binding to target mRNAs. They play a significant role in controlling biological processes including development, metabolism, and stress responses. Our research goal is to understand the gene regulatory network involved in differential gene expression during the process of cold acclimation, a form of phenotypic plasticity that improves cold tolerance in insects. A bioinformatics pipeline was built to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in warm and cold-acclimated flies from the RNA-seq data. We were able to identify 286 genes that exhibited significant differential expression between warm and cold acclimated *D. melanogaster* ($p < 0.001$ and $\log_2\text{fold change} > 2$), with 120 genes downregulated and 166 genes upregulated. The result of the study suggests that by manipulating the miRNA abundance, insects can modulate expression of genes that are responsible for improving their resistance to cold temperatures.

Bossert, Sophia – B-4

Title: Does Calcium Affect Bone Health?

Calcium is important for bone building. The drop in estrogen from menopause makes postmenopausal women have weak and fragile bones, putting these women at risk for fractures and osteoporosis. A meta-analysis was conducted to determine if a higher intake of calcium could offer a simple solution for improving bone health in postmenopausal women. The initial search yielded 512 papers, after vigorous scanning, 13 papers were accepted. The correlation between higher calcium intake and bone health in postmenopausal women was calculated using Fisher's Z. The tau value was above zero, so the random effect size analysis results were used since they accounted for differences in the studies. The Fisher's Z error bars crossed zero, indicating that there is no significant correlation between a higher calcium intake and bone health in postmenopausal women. Further research will need to be conducted to determine an effective way to strengthen the bones of postmenopausal women.

Cornthwaite, Emily – B-5**Title: Predictable food sources drive conflict in ruby-throated hummingbirds (*Archilochus colubris*)**

Food resources drive competition among animal species. For ruby-throated hummingbirds (*Archilochus colubris*), a highly competitive species, conflicts are energetically demanding due to their mode of flight. Here, I test how resource dynamics affect conflict among groups of hummingbirds using one food source. To measure conflict, I focused on displacement behaviours at perches when one hummingbird takes another bird's place. I found that perch conflict decreased when food was unpredictable, and occurred most when food was available under a predictable schedule. This result suggests that conflict depends on what provides the largest benefit and lowest cost. When food was unpredictable and available, competition was costly as it was unknown when food would be available next, making investing time into feeding more beneficial. When food was predictable and available, birds were more willing to engage in conflict, as they could learn when food would be available, and energy could be allocated accordingly.

Dalla Ali, Yasmeen – B-7**Title: Let's Dig In: The Impact of Soil Disturbance on Turtle Nest Predation**

Turtle nests are commonly known for having a high predation rate and a variety of predators, making them especially vulnerable from a young age. However, how do predators know where to locate these turtle eggs? Using Web of Science to search keywords such as predation, cue, and turtle, this meta-analysis investigates whether soil disturbance produced by nesting turtles is used as a cue by predators. By examining several papers that used artificial nests, this meta-analysis uncovers compelling evidence supporting the hypothesis that soil disturbance assists predators in locating nests and increases turtle nest predation. Understanding what makes a nest more vulnerable to predation can lead to better implementation of conservation strategies. Therefore, we suggest future studies should explore the specific cues associated with soil disturbance including visual, chemical, and tactile cues.

Correa, Chris – B-6**Title: Regulation of tyrosyl-trna transferase by cis-resveratrol in the brain**

The basolateral amygdala (BLA) is essential for emotion processing and motivation, regulated by gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) inhibitory neurons, which modulate neuronal excitability. Dysregulation of GABA signaling in the BLA leads to imbalances in amygdalar excitation- inhibition, which is strongly correlated with anxiety and emotion regulation difficulties. Tyrosyl- tRNA synthase (TyrRS) is vital for protein synthesis, with cis-resveratrol influencing its function. Moreover, cis-resveratrol modulates TyrRS, facilitating its interaction with PARP1, a DNA repair enzyme crucial in cellular stress response, this modulation of TyrRS by cis-resveratrol not only affects protein synthesis but also offers neuroprotection in a TyrRS-dependent manner. My study explores the potential of controlling cis-resveratrol to regulate TyrRS activity, thus impacting cellular responses to stress. These findings will provide insights into potential therapeutic strategies for stress-related disorders.

Desbiens, Julia – B-8**Title: Novel Peptide Inhibitors of β -Lactamase TEM-1: A Potential Solution to the Antimicrobial Resistance Crisis**

Antimicrobial resistance is an urgent global healthcare concern, with many frontline antibiotics losing efficacy and multi-drug resistant bacteria on the rise. Among the mechanisms contributing to AMR are β -lactamase enzymes like TEM-1, which degrade β -lactam rings in antibiotics. In this study, we investigate the potential of novel peptides specifically designed to bind and inhibit TEM-1. Utilizing colorimetric assays based on the hydrolysis of nitrocefin at 486nm, we assessed the activity of TEM-1 in the presence of experimental peptides. Our screening process identified three peptide inhibitor candidates capable of reducing overall substrate conversion by ~35-50% ($p < 0.05$ - 0.001). Notably, two inhibitors, EP4 and EP6, significantly reduced TEM-1 conversion rates ($p < 0.05$), underscoring the promise of novel peptides in effectively inhibiting TEM-1 function. By targeting TEM-1, these peptides offer a potential strategy for overcoming β -lactam resistance and revitalizing the efficacy of existing antibiotics. Moreover, they are a significant step towards addressing the pressing challenge of AMR.

Erdely, Katherine – B-10**Title: Trippy Treatments: Investigating the Effectiveness of Psychedelics as a Treatment for Depression**

Depression is a mental illness which causes a decrease in mood and increased suicide risk. Only 25% of people with depression receive treatment and the treatment is only effective 60-80% of the time. I looked for an alternative treatment for depression by performing a meta-analysis. I started with a PICO statement then a research question and search terms. I found 417 articles and screened them for eligibility to reduce them to 18 articles that were used to determine if psychedelics can be used to treat depression. Psychedelics are serotonergic psychedelics which means that they act as an agonist on the serotonin receptors. When activated serotonin helps to increase mood and has been associated with other positive effects. After psychedelic experiences an increase in wellbeing and optimism is observed in humans. Finally, depression was measured to be lower after taking psychedelics and these results were determined to be statistically significant.

Donohue, Margaret – B-9**Title: Analyzing the Effects of Face Masks on the Spread of COVID-19**

In December 2019, a virus, COVID-19 began a worldwide pandemic. Many protocols were created to reduce the spread of the virus including limiting the number of people indoors, social distancing, and face masks. I conducted a fixed and random effects meta-analysis to determine if masks effectively reduce the spread of COVID-19. Initially, 743 publications regarding COVID-19 were screened yielding 10 empirical research papers addressing the impact of face masks on COVID-19 virus proliferation. Next, I constructed a Forest Plot that analyzes the significance of each paper. The fixed effects meta-analysis supported the thesis that masks do reduce the spread of COVID, but the random effects model, while also supportive, was less conclusive. I concluded that, for the most part, face masks do seem to aid in reducing the spread of COVID-19; however, further research will be needed to confirm this assertion.

Gessese, Tadesse – B-11**Title: Development of a Machine Learning Model for the Prediction of Cell-Penetrating Peptide Sequences**

Cell penetrating peptides (CPPs) are a class of molecules that can traverse cell membranes, crucial for drug delivery and therapeutic interventions. Their capacity to transport therapeutic agents underscores the need for advanced methods to identify CPPs within peptide libraries accurately. In this work, we develop a novel machine learning approach to accurately predict whether a peptide can penetrate cells, distinguishing between cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs) and non-cell-penetrating peptides. Our dataset comprises of 401 sequences of each type, serving as the foundation for model training. We employed a genetic algorithm for feature selection to enhance the predictive accuracy and efficiency of the model. Subsequent evaluation involved comparing various classifiers, including the Lazy K Star (88% accuracy), J48 (84.5%), Naive Bayes (86%), Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) (88%), and Random Forest (90%), which emerged as the superior model. This study contributes to the field by offering a high accuracy tool for CPPs.

Huynh, Tianna – B-12**Title: Aggressive or greedy? A study on how resources affect conflict over food in ruby-throated hummingbirds.**

Competition is widespread among species, including interspecific and intraspecific interactions. We examined intraspecific competition among ruby-throated hummingbirds, specifically their aggressive behaviors in defending nectar sources. We hypothesized that food availability and predictability potentially influence these behaviors over time due to learning and seasonal factors. Experimentally, we manipulated resource environments and observed conflicts, specifically when the birds displaced each other at a shared feeder. Treatments included predictable food changes every 10 minutes and unpredictable changes every 5 to 25 minutes, with alternating "food on" intervals containing sugar water and "food off" intervals with water only. We predicted more frequent displacements during "food on" intervals and more in the unpredictable treatment. Displacement was higher during "food on" times and, unexpectedly, they were more common during predictable treatments. This could be attributed to episodic memory and diminishing resources. Future research should explore behavioral variations and the impact of sex hormones on competition dynamics.

Kamm-Ramirez, Nadine – B-14**Title: DROSHA Knockout Increases the Susceptibility of HCT116 to Actinomycin-D Induced Apoptosis**

Apoptosis is a form of programmed cell death mediated by cysteine proteases (caspases), which is thought to play a role in determining the response of cancer cells to chemotherapeutic drugs. MicroRNAs (miRNAs), short non-coding RNAs, influence gene expression and are known to affect anti-cancer drug responses. Previous investigations in our laboratory assessed drug response in HCT116 cells and isogenic DROSHA gene-deleted cells, which are unable to produce canonical miRNAs. It was revealed that DROSHA-null cells had increased sensitivity to chemotherapeutic agents, including actinomycin-D (ACT-D), compared to the parental line. To determine if this sensitivity is due to caspase-dependent apoptosis, we evaluated both cell lines' responses to ACT-D with and without Z-VAD-FMK, a pan-caspase inhibitor. This inhibitor effectively blocked caspase-dependent apoptosis in both cell lines. Our findings suggest that both cell lines undergo apoptosis and that the DROSHA-deleted cells are more susceptible to this form of cell death induced by ACT-D.

Jenkins, Danielle – B-13**Title: Investigating the Mass Death of the Nobel Fan Mollusks (*Pinna nobilis*)**

In 2019 *Pinna nobilis* (*P. nobilis*) was determined to be an endangered species, by 2020, 99% of this species had been wiped out in the Adriatic Sea. *Haplosporidium pinnae*, a parasitic bacterium has been suggested as the leading cause. I completed a meta-analysis to investigate the question does the presence of *H. pinnae* lead to the death of *P. nobilis*? The forest plot from the meta-analysis indicated no effect of *H. pinnae* on *P. nobilis*. This meta-analysis was done on a small number of papers, more research on this topic is necessary. Despite the results it is critical the mass mortality of *P. nobilis* is stopped before it leads to permanent damage in its ecosystem. Further research should investigate the infection of *P. nobilis* with *H. pinnae*, preventative methods will lead to the *P. nobilis* population recovering.

Lagrove, Kennedy – B-15**Title: Creatine Supplementation: The Effects on Body Fat Percentage**

Creatine supplementation is one of the most common practices in the fitness world and has gained popularity among gym enthusiasts looking to optimize their workouts and gains. While creatine supplementation is often promoted to reduce body fat, evidence remains inconclusive, and studies report contradicting results from one another. We delve into the complicated relationship between creatine supplementation and body fat percentage by conducting a meta-analysis of fourteen carefully selected studies. By critically assessing study designs, sample sizes, and outcome measures, the research aims to address the true impact of creatine supplementation on body fat percentage. Results suggest that there is a slight favour towards a decrease in body fat percentage when taking creatine supplementation, and results of fixed and random effect models are the same. Understanding the significance of the findings and reflecting on how the results could impact the future of fitness is important.

Laribi, Tarek – B-16**Title: Liposome-based nano carriers to encapsulate odd chain fatty acids, enhancing their bioavailability**

Odd-chain fatty acids (OCFAs) have an odd number of carbon atoms in their carbon chain, making them distinct. Although OCFAs are naturally found in lower quantities due to factors in their biosynthesis, dietary sources, and microbial production, they show potential in various therapeutic applications because of their unique properties. Encapsulating OCFAs offers several benefits, including improved insulin sensitivity, reduced inflammation, and a potentially lower risk of cardiovascular diseases. However, clinical limitations arise due to factors such as their abundance in nature, poor solubility, and rapid degradation in the gastrointestinal tract (GI). Liposome-based nanocarriers provide a promising solution by encapsulating OCFAs and preventing their degradation in the GI. Liposomes act as carrier vesicles that encapsulate specific compounds based on their physical and chemical properties, allowing them to be tailored to various functions. Selecting factors like lipid types and particle size alters liposome properties, including size, stability, and release kinetics, improving bioavailability. Surface modifications of liposomes enhance OCFAs delivery, enhancing therapeutic effectiveness.

Liebig, Jason – B-18**Title: Creatine supplementation's effectiveness on muscle gain in humans**

Creatine is an intermediate in the metabolism of skeletal muscle tissue within humans. The supplementing of creatine dietarily, paired with strength training, has been attributed to increased skeletal muscle gain. However, there is uncertainty as to whether supplementing creatine is effective at increasing the amount of muscle gained through regular training. To investigate creatine's effects on muscle gain within humans, a meta-analysis of the literature following a PRISMA methodology was completed. 557 primary literature articles were identified through web of science. Screening and eligibility processes resulted in the inclusion of 10 final articles, relevant for statistical analysis. Hedges G was calculated as a measure of effects size for muscle gain between groups supplementing creatine, and a control group. The random effects, and fixed effects values are positive. The results indicate that supplementing creatine does increase muscle gain in humans.

Lemieux, Amelie – B-17**Title: How prescribed burns affect forest diversity: A meta-analysis**

Wildfires increase biodiversity by promoting natural succession providing favourable conditions for new floral species to grow. Succession therefore produces heterogenous environments, thus promoting the diversification of floral and faunal species. Recently, prescribed burns have been recognized as a forest management regime. Prescribed burns are employed following a timber harvest to mimic wildfire succession, or to moderate fuel reduction and severe wildfires. Given our understanding of wildfires and their positive effects on biodiversity, this meta-analysis aims to find out how prescribed burns affect forest diversity. 691 relevant sources were first obtained from the Web of Science, from which they were further refined to 22 primary sources measuring species richness before and after prescribed burns. The results demonstrate a mean increase in forest diversity after samples were treated with prescribed burns, which provides insightful information regarding how we may shift gears towards more sustainable forest management.

Marshall, Kyle – B-19**Title: Biomechanics of Locust Swimming**

Swimming is a fundamental locomotory mode for many animals, both aquatic and terrestrial. That said, it is interesting biomechanically speaking, to wonder if an exclusively terrestrial and often stated desert species is capable of swimming. My thesis objective was to determine if locusts were capable of moving in a manner consistent with goal-oriented locomotion (i.e. swimming) in water, and to characterize the kinematics of locusts when placed in water. Adult African migratory locusts (*Locusta migratoria*) were filmed from above when placed in 10 cm of water in a 28 X 54 cm glass tank. All Locusts observed, clearly showed goal-directed locomotory movements consisted with a 'swimming behaviour'. The movements were not similar walking or jumping locomotion. Abdomen-Femur angles were correlated with swim velocity, and hind-leg kinematics overall suggested a mechanism for changing direction and attitude during trials. These findings contribute to an understudied behaviour and establish a foundation for further research.

McLean, Bradley – B-20**Title: A common sleep support has unclear effects on male fertility.**

Male fertility is decreasing around the world, and the cause is unknown. I was interested in finding a supplement that can improve male fertility. Endogenous melatonin is beneficial to sperm quality and sex hormone secretion, so the purpose of this meta-analysis was to find out if the consumption of exogenous melatonin could improve these qualities further. I screened 614 papers for viability, and I examined 10 papers. From each paper, I calculated the Hedge's g effect size, and I weighed the papers by variance. I then analyzed the data with a random effects model and a fixed effects model. In both cases, I was unable to reject the null hypothesis that melatonin does not affect male fertility. Current research indicates consuming melatonin does not improve male fertility.

Morden, Eric – B-22**Title: Impact of drought on bread wheat grain weight**

Bread wheat is one of the most common and most important crops in the world, being the most vital source of nutrition for over a third of the human population. However, climate change is causing drought to occur more frequently around the world, and studies have shown that drought has a significant negative effect on wheat grain yield. However, there is not much research that focuses on the impact drought has on grain weight, even though grain weight is an important aspect of flour production because a grain yield with larger grains produces more flour than a grain yield with smaller grains. A meta-analysis was performed on papers from studies that measured the effect of drought on 1000-grain weight. The forest plot that was developed had both a fixed and a random effect size of less than zero, supporting the hypothesis that drought causes a decrease in 1000-grain weight.

Moran, James – B-21**Title: Computational screening to identify genes involved in DNA repair in *Arabidopsis thaliana***

The repair of damaged DNA is an essential function for living organisms. While great strides have been made in understanding this process in animal and yeast models, our knowledge in plant DNA repair is not as developed. Plants face many sources of DNA damage which they cannot so easily avoid: UV radiation from sunlight, reactive oxygen species produced endogenously by their mitochondria and chloroplasts, reactive oxygen species accumulated while under conditions of cold, heat, or salt stress. Understanding plant DNA repair is particularly relevant as the accumulation of DNA damage can negatively impact the growth and yield of agronomically important species. In this study, a broad classification of genes related to DNA repair in the model dicot *Arabidopsis thaliana* was conducted using gene ontology and gene enrichment analysis. The results of this broad classification serve to elucidate pathways for further study in plant DNA damage response and repair.

Morrison, Grace – B-23**Title: The Impact of No-Till Agriculture on Soil Carbon Sequestration in USA and Canada**

Soil is a vital part of our ecosystem. Soil can influence the amount of carbon that is in our atmosphere through the carbon cycle. Carbon sequestration, or carbon capturing in soil, is a phenomenon that has been researched for many years, particularly in its application to climate change. Soil scientists have looked at how an agricultural practice called no-till can increase the amount of carbon that is captured in soil. This meta-analysis compiles several sources that have researched this topic and concludes that there is an overarching trend in the sources. The meta-analysis concluded that no-till agriculture does increase the amount of carbon that soil sequesters. The author used a t-test analysis to compare levels of CO₂ captured in tilled fields and CO₂ in non-tilled fields. The knowledge that no-till agriculture can decrease our atmospheric carbon offers a new approach to combatting climate change.

Nwabueze, Jacqueline – B-24**Title: The Influence of Screen Time on Adolescent Sleep Quality: A Meta-Analysis**

In a time when screens dominate our daily lives, concerns about their impact on human health are pervasive. These concerns are especially pervasive when discussing adolescents, whose minds and bodies are not fully developed. Previous findings detailing the disruptive effects of blue light emitted from screens on melatonin production prompt a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between screen use and sleep quality. This meta-analysis assessed whether increased screen time was associated with poor sleep quality, measured through sleep duration, in adolescents. Analyzing data from 23 primary studies, the results of this meta-analysis were inconclusive. While some evidence suggested a negative correlation between screen time and sleep duration, others hinted at a more positive influence. These findings highlight the complex relationship between screen time and sleep quality, emphasizing the need for further research to fully understand how ever-prevalent screens impact human health.

Rice, Kinly – B-26**Title: The Effectiveness of Masks in Reducing the Spread of Covid-19**

The Covid-19 pandemic originated from the rapid widespread transmission of the novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2. This meta-analysis investigates the effectiveness of masks in reducing the spread of Covid-19. A literary search on Carleton's Web of Science yielded 1000 primary research articles surrounding mask mandates and Covid-19. Exclusion criteria reduced the study size to 10 records, which were processed and formatted into a forest plot to display overall summary estimates. The results showed a positive effect and tau value of <0.001 , indicating that masks are effective at reducing the spread of Covid-19. The overall effect size estimate indicated that the results are statistically significant. The knowledge gained through this analysis can aid in preventing future outbreaks and developing effective health interventions against future pandemics. The findings of the study extend beyond Covid-19 by offering a valuable tool for addressing other respiratory viruses or airborne diseases that are transmitted through respiratory droplets.

Phillips, Ally – B-25**Title: Burmese Pythons in the Florida Everglades: Ecological Menace and Native Species Conservation Imperatives**

The Florida Everglades face a severe ecological threat from invasive Burmese pythons *Python bivittatus*. Introduced through the pet trade, Burmese constrictors have rapidly proliferated, disrupting the Everglades' delicate ecosystem. With a voracious appetite, Burmese pythons prey on native wildlife, decimating populations of mammals, birds, and reptiles. The pythons' unchecked expansion has triggered a cascading effect, contributing to the decline of several keystone species. Effective management strategies are imperative to mitigate the ecological damage caused by invasive Burmese pythons. My comprehensive review calls for an understanding of the python's ecological impact, population dynamics, and dispersal patterns is essential for targeted eradication efforts. My review synthesizes existing research on Burmese pythons in the Florida Everglades, highlighting key findings and identifying knowledge gaps crucial for the development of evidence-based conservation initiatives.

Rix, Tamaryn – B-27**Title: The Impacts of Daylight-Saving Time Transitions on Cardiovascular Health: A Meta-Analysis**

Daylight-Saving Time (DST) transitions have been linked to various adverse health effects, including impacts on cardiovascular health. Sleep deprivation of one hour caused by the Spring DST transition can contribute to cardiovascular abnormalities. In this meta-analysis, I aimed to determine whether there is an increase in the number of cardiovascular abnormalities in the week following the Spring DST change. I identified 932 articles using the database Web of Science. After screening I included 14 relevant articles in this meta-analysis. I calculated effect sizes using Hedges' g , and the random effects meta-analysis model revealed a positive effect of 0.03 (95% CL [0.01, 0.04]). These results show a statistically significant increase in the number of cardiovascular abnormalities in the week following the Spring DST change. Further research and public health interventions are needed to address the adverse effects of DST transitions on cardiovascular health.

Saunders, Nolan – B-28**Title: The Connectivity of Forest Canopy Cover and Freshwater Biodiversity**

Canopy cover, defined as tree foliage extent, significantly shapes the health and diversity of freshwater ecosystems by influencing light penetration, temperature regulation, and community composition. Despite established understanding in terrestrial ecosystems, further targeted investigations are needed to discern its direct impact on freshwater habitats. My meta-analysis explores the correlation between canopy cover and freshwater biodiversity in terms of species richness, abundance, and the Shannon diversity index across macroinvertebrates, amphibians, fish, and riparian vegetation. Using search terms, 510 records were identified, with eligibility determined based on data availability, outcome, and publication type. Nine papers were selected for meta-analysis, resulting in the random effects meta-analysis with no significant correlation between canopy cover and freshwater biodiversity, and a moderate positive correlation in fixed effects meta-analysis. Further research and conservation efforts on freshwater canopy cover are necessary to preserve habitat connectivity and ecosystem services.

Singh, James – B-30**Title: Investigating the Redox Cycling of Arsenic in *Herminiimonas arsenicoxydans***

Arsenic is a Class I carcinogen that has been leaching into groundwater supplies due to industrial practices. This study investigated the physiological and genetic effects of arsenic exposure on microbes that possess the ability to survive in environments with heavy metals. *Herminiimonas arsenicoxydans* was selected as it can use arsenic in different redox reactions based on the species of arsenic present. Initially, toxicity was evaluated using both arsenate and arsenite in a complex-defined media. The results showed that 2 μM of arsenite and 6 μM of arsenate induced toxicity. Following this, chemical speciation work using a novel colorimetric assay was done to understand the redox cycling of arsenic in this environment. As well, qRT-PCR was used to observe the expression levels of their arsenic cycling enzymes. Characterization of *H. arsenicoxydans* survival in these environments offers insight into the use of microbes for bioremediation in these contaminated groundwater sites.

Shareef, Rizwan – B-29**Title: Deciphering Dysregulation: PAX7 methylation disruption leads to reduced differentiation potential**

Muscle stem cells in Duchenne's Muscular Dystrophy (DMD) exhibit heightened proliferation and ability to give rise to progenitors. Paired-Box 7 (PAX7), a key marker in these cells, undergoes methylation by Coactivator Arginine Methyltransferase 1 (CARM1), which recruits histone modifiers to trigger activation of target genes for differentiation. In DMD however, the CARM1:PAX7 interaction is disrupted, fostering increased proliferation and maintenance of the stem cell state. We hypothesize that the loss of PAX7 methylation disrupts its interactome leading to impaired progression towards differentiation. To investigate, we employed BioID and mass spectrometry to identify proteins binding PAX7 versus proteins binding an unmethylated mutant (PAX7-4RK). Mass spectrometry revealed notable hits associated with the SIN3B and KTM2C/D COMPASS complex specifically binding PAX7-4RK. These results suggest enhanced H3K4 mono-methylation at myogenic promoters reducing expression and potentially enforcing stemness. Future research should corroborate these findings in wild-type and DMD myoblasts through co-immunoprecipitation and proximity ligation assays.

Steenbakkers, Marin – B-31**Title: Targeted Therapy Outperforms Chemotherapy in Reducing HER2-Positive Breast Cancer Progression**

Chemotherapy, a traditional treatment for HER2-positive breast cancer, lacks cell specificity and can result in adverse effects on healthy cells. Fortunately, targeted therapies like Trastuzumab offer a more precise approach by selectively binding to over-expressed receptors on breast cancer cells. While Trastuzumab is most often administered alongside chemotherapy because of the combination's synergistic effects, the toxicity of chemotherapy remains a concern for patient quality of life. This meta-analysis comprised of 10 primary research articles aimed to compare disease progression event occurrences in patients treated with either Trastuzumab or with chemotherapy alone. The findings indicated that Trastuzumab is associated with reduced disease progression events, suggesting that the generalized approach of chemotherapy should be reconsidered. Instead, future studies should focus on exploring potential synergies between Trastuzumab and other targeted medicines, aiming to move away from treatment plans that harm healthy cells.

Velasquez, Jahnessa – B-33**Title: Comparative Neuroembryology of the Salamanders *Ambystoma mexicanum* and *Plethodon cinereus***

Understanding differences in the brains of species provides insights into evolutionary adaptations and neurobiological diversity. This study investigates brain morphology in two salamanders with distinct ecological niches and life histories: the axolotl (*Ambystoma mexicanum*) and the red-backed salamander (*Plethodon cinereus*). Using micro-CT scanning, brain regions were identified and compared to one another. We found that *P. cinereus* exhibited relatively larger optic lobes, smaller trigeminal nerves, and a slower development rate for its midbrain. These are interpreted as relating to its terrestrial habitat. On the other hand, *A. mexicanum* exhibited smaller optic lobes, larger olfactory lobes, and more prominent trigeminal nerves, which alludes to the fact that they rely heavily on their olfactory senses in their low-light, aquatic environments. These findings contribute to our understanding of brain evolution in salamanders, and amphibians as a whole by revealing potential neural adaptations linked to ecological and physiological traits.

Sultan, Nooran – B-32**Title: Exploring Molecular Mechanisms of Cold Tolerance in Mountain Pine Beetles: A Study on Trehalase Gene Variations**

Mountain pine beetles (MPB) are bark beetles that infest pine trees, primarily in Western North America, and cause tree mortality within a year of infestation. Originally confined to British Columbia due to colder climates, they have demonstrated the ability to expand away from their historic regions to Alberta, impacting millions of hectares of land. This study tackles this issue by examining the trehalase gene, which encodes the enzyme responsible for the breakdown of the sugar trehalose, a molecule crucial for carbohydrate metabolism and stress recovery. Genetic analysis involved genotyping the trehalase gene in a sample of 245 beetles from 11 different sites across British Columbia and Alberta. These samples were then tested for Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium, and the spatial distribution of the allele frequencies was mapped. Insights into the genetic mechanisms behind the cold tolerance of MPB could aid in the development of targeted pest controls.

Wood-Lyons, Isabel – B-34**Alternative Concussion Diagnosis: Analysis of Saccadic Movement Post Concussion**

Concussions are a common athletic injury that affected 573,000 Canadians in the last year. One of the current standards of assessment, the vestibular ocular motor test (VOMS), is reliant on the individual reporting symptoms and the intra-individual reliability issues due to its subjective administration. The objective of this study was to determine if eye tracking in response to specific visual stimuli correlated with the self-proclaimed history of concussions in a population of Varsity athletes. Eye movements were tracked and assessed using an open-sourced Tracker software. The data displayed that individuals with a history of concussions, especially those with multiple, had difficulty holding gaze, and had larger deviations in tracking the target. This work aids in developing an improved diagnosis protocol that will be able to monitor levels of recovery through digital eye tracking.

Message to our Amazing June 2024 Graduates

A heartfelt thank you to everyone who joined us in celebrating our 2024 Biology Undergraduate Research!

Today, to all capstone students, we are celebrating your outstanding achievements. Your hard work, determination, and enthusiasm have truly inspired us all. As you start your next chapters, we wish you continued success and happiness!

Thank you for making this event memorable!

Department of Biology

Carleton University

April 12th, 2024

